

A new acetophenone derivative from *Artemisia maritima*

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A new acetophenone derivative 2-hydroxy-4,6-dimethoxyacetophenone (**1**) along with α -santonin and 5-hydroxy-7,4'-dimethoxy-flavone have been isolated from the aerial parts of *Artemisia maritima*.

Artemisia maritima (family Compositae) is deobstruent, stomachic, laxative and tonic¹. The decoction of the leaves is used in ague and in intermittent and remittent fever. The plant is commercially exploited for santonin, a sesquiterpene lactone which is very effective in its action on roundworms and also reported to be a potent antifertility agent in mice². Here we report the isolation of a new acetophenone derivative. 2-hydroxy-4,6-dimethoxyacetophenone besides known α -santonin and 5-hydroxy-7,4'-dimethoxyflavone from the aerial parts of this plant.

Compound **1**, m.p. 78–79°, C₁₀H₁₂O₄ (M⁺ 196) appeared as a purple spot on TLC under UV-light and gave positive FeCl₃ test for phenols. Its IR spectrum revealed the presence of conjugated and chelated ketone (1622 cm⁻¹), and hydroxyl group at 3440 cm⁻¹. The ¹³C NMR, DEPT experiment displayed total ten carbon atoms with eleven directly attached protons. The chemical shift values suggested the presence of three oxygen bearing aryl carbons, two aryl-methines and a non-protonated aryl carbon atom, thus identifying the presence of tetrasubstituted phenyl ring system. The other ¹³C NMR features included a ketone (δ 203.1), two methoxy group (δ 55.5 each) and a methyl (δ 32.8). In ¹H NMR two doublets at δ 5.91 (*J* 3 Hz) and 6.05 (*J* 3 Hz) were assigned for *meta*-coupled protons of aromatic ring system. A downfield D₂O exchangeable singlet at δ 14.03 was according to the OH proton chelated with ketone. Thus the compound was inferred to be an acetophenone derivative, where COCH₃ protons resonated at δ 2.61 and methyl carbon attached to carbonyl group appeared at δ 32.8 in ¹³C NMR. It afforded a monoacetate on acetylation and gave positive Gibbs's test for unsubstituted *para*-phenol system³. Thus compound **1** was identified as 2-hydroxy-4,6-dimethoxyacetophenone^{4,5}, a new natural product. The compound seems to be the biochemical precursor of flavone 5-hydroxy-7,4'-dimethoxyflavone isolated from this plant.

Compound **2**, m.p. 172–173°, C₁₅H₁₈O₃ (M⁺ 1246) was identified as α -santonin on the basis of spectral studies and comparison with authentic sample.

Compound **3**, m.p. 160–162°, C₁₇H₁₄O₅ (M⁺ 298), gave positive FeCl₃ and Mg + HCl test, indicative of flavone skeleton. The spectral analyses led to the identification of compound **3** as 5-hydroxy-7,4'-dimethoxyflavone, also known as apigenin-7,4'-dimethylether.

Experimental

The plant was collected from Kashmir valleys and identified at Botany and Pharmacognosy Department of Central Institute of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants, Lucknow. All m.p.s. are uncorrected. TLC was carried out on precoated silica gel-G plates (E. Merck) and spots were visualized in UV-light and spraying with 10% H₂SO₄ solution followed by heating at 110°. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1710 FT spectrophotometer, UV spectra on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda Bio 20 spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) at 300 MHz with TMS as internal standard and ¹³C NMR spectra (CDCl₃) at 75 MHz on a Bruker Avance Drx (300 MHz) instrument where residual solvent peaks were used as internal reference, and EIMS on a JEOL-JMSD-100 spectrometer (70 eV).

Air-dried aerial parts (500 g) of *A. maritima*, constituting inflorescence, small red stem and leaves were powdered and extracted with *n*-hexane (5 × 0.5 cm³) in the soxhlet apparatus for 8 h. The extract was evaporated under vacuum to get a residue (22.5 g) which was dissolved in *n*-hexane : ethyl acetate mixture (7 : 3; 250 ml) and then partitioned with aqueous acetonitrile (1 : 4; 4 × 150 ml). In the aqueous acetonitrile phase (600 ml), sodium chloride (6.0 g) was added to separate water. The separated acetonitrile part was dried over anhyd. Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure to get a residue (9.0 g) which was column chromatographed over silica gel (60–120 mesh) using *n*-

hexane containing increasing amount of ethyl acetate as eluant. Fractions (100 ml each) were collected and monitored by TLC examination to yield three pure compounds **1** (0.10 g), **2** (2.5 g) and **3** (0.40 g).

2-Hydroxy-4,6-dimethoxyacetophenone (1) : White crystalline powder, m.p. 78–79° (Found : C, 61.26; H, 6.35. Required : C, 61.22; H, 6.16%); R_f 0.51 (EtOAc : *n*-hexane 10 : 90); ν_{\max} 3440, 3020, 2927, 1622, 1595, 1419, 1274, 1215, 763, 671 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (CDCl_3) 6.05 (1H, d, J 3 Hz, H-3), 5.91 (1H, d, J 3 Hz, H-5), 2.61 (3H, s, COCH_3), 14.03 (1H, s, D_2O exchangeable OH-2), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH_3 -4), 3.82 (3H, s, OCH_3 -6); $^{13}\text{C NMR } \delta$ (CDCl_3) 105.9 (C-1), 162.9 (C-2), 93.4 (C-3), 167.5 (C-4), 90.7 (C-5), 166.0 (C-6), 203.1 (CO), 32.8 (COCH_3), 55.5 ($\text{OCH}_3 \times 2$); m/z (%) 196 $[\text{M}]^+$ $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ (70.7), 181 $[\text{M}-\text{CH}_3]^+$ (100), 166 $[\text{M}-30]$ (14.1), 151, 138, 123, 95, 43.

Acetylation of 1 : Compound **1** (10.0 mg) was dissolved in pyridine (1.0 ml) and acetic anhydride (0.5 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature for complete acetylation. The excess water was then added and the mixture was extracted with CHCl_3 . The chloroform extract was washed in sequence with 5% HCl , H_2O , 5% NaHCO_3 , H_2O and dried over anhyd. Na_2SO_4 . Removal of solvent yielded the monoacetate **1a** (8.0 mg), m.p. 101–103°; R_f 0.17 (EtOAc : *n*-hexane, 10 : 90); ν_{\max} 2925, 2352, 1771, 1683, 1612, 1253, 1200, 1098 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (CDCl_3) 6.36 (1H, d J 1.8 Hz, H-3), 6.22 (1H, d J 1.8 Hz, H-5), 2.47 (3H, s, COCH_3), 2.25 (3H, s, OCOCH_3), 3.84 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.81 (3H, s, OCH_3); m/z 238 $[\text{M}]^+$ $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$.

5-Hydroxy-7,4'-dimethoxyflavone (3) : Yellow needles,

m.p. 160–162°; R_f 0.66 (MeOH : CHCl_3 , 5 : 95); λ_{\max} (MeOH) 269.5, 327 nm; ν_{\max} 3350–3100, 1625, 1616, 1400, 1275, 1166, 835 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (CDCl_3) 6.58 (1H, s, H-3), 6.48 (1H, d, J 2.1 Hz, H-6), 6.36 (1H, d, J 2.1 Hz, H-8), 7.85 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, H-2',6'), 7.02 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, H-3',5'), 12.82 (1H, s, D_2O exchangeable OH-5), 3.89 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.88 (3H, s, OCH_3); $^{13}\text{C NMR } \delta$ (CDCl_3) 164.6 (C-2), 104.4 (C-3), 183.0 (C-4), 157.8 (C-5), 92.6 (C-6), 162.7 (C-7), 98.0 (C-8), 161.4 (C-9), 105.2 (C-10), 123.0 (C-1'), 128.1 (C-2',6'), 114.5 (C-3',5'), 160.4 (C-4'), 55.5, 55.8 (2 \times OCH_3 at C-7, C-4'); m/z (%) 298 $[\text{M}]^+$ $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$ (100), 283, $[\text{M}-15]^+$, 269 (41.5), 255 (33), 166 (23.5), 138 (27.6), 132 (33.9), 117, 95, 89, 69.

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References

1. "The Wealth of India : Raw Material". C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1985, Vol. 1A.
2. R. N. Chopra, S. L. Nayar and I. C. Chopra, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants". C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956.
3. J. C. Dacre, *Anal. Chem.*, 1971, 43, 589.
4. S. Ghosal, P. Mittal, Y. Kumar and S. K. Singh, *Phytochemistry*, 1989, 28, 3193.
5. A. K. Singh, V. Pathak and P. K. Agrawal, *Phytochemistry*, 1997, 44, 555.